

Awareness On Medicinal Applications Of Selenium Nanoparticles Among Dental Students

Research Article

Dhanraj Ganapathy^{1*}, Martina Catherine², Ashok Velayudhan³¹Professor & Head of Department, Department of Prosthodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Chennai, India.²Tutor, Department of Prosthodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Chennai, India.³Professor, Department of Prosthodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences (SIMATS), Saveetha University, 162, Poonamallee High Road, Velappanchavadi, Chennai - 600077.

Abstract

Introduction: Nanoparticles (NPs) are used to minimise toxicity, increase bioactivity, improve targeting, and modulate the release profile of the encapsulated moiety in a variety of ways. Selenium (Se) NPs hold a special place among NPs due to their distinct bioactivities in nanoforms.

Aim: This survey was conducted for assessing the awareness about medicinal application of Selenium nanoparticles amongst dental students.

Materials and Method: A cross-section research was conducted with a self-administered questionnaire containing ten questions distributed amongst 100 dental students. The questionnaire assessed the awareness about Selenium nanoparticles therapy in medical applications, their pro oxidant properties, anti-cancer activities, anti-diabetic properties and their role in targeted drug therapy, the responses were recorded and analysed.

Results: 12% of the respondents were aware of the medicinal applications of Selenium Nanoparticles. 9% were aware of prooxidant properties of Selenium Nanoparticles, 9% were aware of anti-cancer properties of Selenium Nanoparticles, 6% were aware of anti-diabetic properties of Selenium Nanoparticles and 4% were aware of their role in targeted drug therapy.

Conclusion: There is limited awareness amongst dental students about use of Selenium nanoparticles therapy in medical applications. Enhanced awareness initiatives and dental educational programmes together with increased importance for curriculum improvements that further promote knowledge and awareness of Selenium nanoparticles therapy.

Keywords: Awareness; Selenium; Nanoparticles; Students; Medicinal; Cancer.

Introduction

In the last three decades, nanotechnology has revolutionised drug discovery and development by unlocking several previously closed doors in disease pathophysiology and therapy choices [1]. Nanotechnology is concerned with submicroscopic particles with a minimum dimension of 100 nanometers. Polymers, dendrimers, liposomes, metal nanoparticles, silicon, and carbon-based nanomaterials have all been successfully employed as therapeutic agents and drug delivery vehicles [2]. Nanoparticles (NPs) are extremely unique due to their small size, large surface area, surface charge, surface chemistry, solubility, and multifunctionality. NPs

have demonstrated their efficacy as medication carriers by delivering therapeutic compounds with great success. Nanomedicine is the use of nanotechnology-based techniques and methodologies for the treatment, diagnosis, monitoring, and control of biological systems in medical research and clinical practice [3].

Se is a semi-solid metal that resembles sulphur and tellurium and is commonly observed as a red coloured powder, black in vitreous form, and metallic grey in crystalline form. Immunomodulatory activity and sperm motility orchestration are two important roles played by selenoproteins [4]. The human genome has 25 selenoprotein genes. Various antioxidant enzymes, such as glutathione peroxidase, thioredoxin reductase, and selenoprotein P, incorpo-

***Corresponding Author:**

Dhanraj Ganapathy,
Professor & Head of Department, Department of Prosthodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences, Chennai, India.
Tel: 9841504523
E-mail: dhanrajganapathy@yahoo.co.in

Received: September 12, 2021

Accepted: September 20, 2021

Published: September 21, 2021

Citation: Dhanraj Ganapathy, Martina Catherine, Ashok Velayudhan. Awareness On Medicinal Applications Of Selenium Nanoparticles Among Dental Students. *Int J Dentistry Oral Sci.* 2021;8(9):4372-4375. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.19070/2377-8075-21000890>

Copyright: Dhanraj Ganapathy©2021. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

rate se as selenocysteine. All of these enzymes' redox centres are selenium, which is required for their metabolic function. Sodium selenite, selenomethionine, and monomethylated Se are some of the other major Se-containing chemicals that can act as anticancer agents through various pathways.

Glutathione peroxidases and deiodinases are selenoenzymes that are essential for a variety of metabolic activities, including the physiological antioxidant defence system. Depending on the dose, duration, and oxidation state, it exhibits unique antioxidant and pro-oxidant actions [5]. In a mouse model, the application of SeNPs greatly lowers the death caused by acute Se poisoning by up to four times. Furthermore, as evidenced by indicators of hepatotoxicity, the liver damage associated with high doses of Se are significantly reduced when SeNPs are used [6]. When compared to other Se species, SeNPs have excellent anticancer efficacy and lower safety issues. SeNPs have been utilised to treat cancer, diabetes, inflammatory disorders, liver fibrosis, and drug-induced toxicities, among other diseases [7, 8]. SeNPs scavenge the free radicals in vitro in size dependent manner (5 nm–200 nm). Our research experience has prompted us in pursuing this research [9–20]. This survey was conducted for assessing the awareness about medicinal application of Selenium nanoparticles amongst dental students.

Materials and Methods

A cross-section research was conducted with a self-administered questionnaire containing ten questions distributed amongst 100

dental students. The questionnaire assessed the awareness about Selenium nanoparticles therapy in medical applications, their prooxidant properties, anti-cancer activities, anti-diabetic properties and their role in targeted drug therapy, the responses were recorded and analysed.

Results

12% of the respondents were aware of the medicinal applications of Selenium Nanoparticles (Fig 1). 9 % were aware of prooxidant properties of Selenium Nanoparticles (Fig 2), 9 % were aware of anti-cancer properties of Selenium Nanoparticles (Fig 3), 6 % were aware of anti-diabetic properties of Selenium Nanoparticles (Fig 4) and 4% were aware of their role in targeted drug therapy (Fig 5).

Discussion

SeNPs have been studied in a variety of illness conditions due to their superior characteristics over Se. SeNPs provide increased bioavailability with the added benefit of reduced toxicity. In a number of pathological diseases, the prooxidant and antioxidant actions give distinct routes for investigation. The use of SeNPs for various therapeutic applications, including antibacterial, anti-cancer, anti-diabetic, and anti-inflammatory action, is discussed in this section.

Chemically produced SeNPs were observed to alter oestrogen receptor-alpha signalling in MCF-7 breast cancer cells and lead

Figure 1. Awareness of the medicinal applications of Selenium Nanoparticles.

Figure 2. Awareness of the prooxidant properties of Selenium Nanoparticles.

Figure 3. Awareness of the anti-cancer properties of Selenium Nanoparticles

Figure 4. Awareness of the anti-diabetic properties of Selenium Nanoparticles.

to enhanced expression of cytochrome C, Bax, and P-p38 compared to MDA-MB 231 cells, according to Vekariya *et al.*, [9]. In a separate study, SeNPs were found to significantly reduce adhesion force, induce apoptosis and necrosis in MCF-7 cells, and decrease CD44 expression; caused disorganisation and dysregulation of intracellular cytoskeleton F-actin in MCF-7 cells; and caused disorganisation and dysregulation of intracellular cytoskeleton F-actin in MCF-7 cells [21]. SeNPs inhibit the matrix metalloproteinase-2 expression which is mainly involved in tumor invasion, metastasis and angiogenesis in fibro-sarcoma cell lines [22]. SeNPs showed promising anti-proliferative activity and inhibition of HeLa cells during S phase [23]. SeNPs were produced intracellularly from the haloarchaeon *Halococcus salifodinae* BK18 with the help of the enzyme NADH-dependent nitrate reductase in another work. SeNPs demonstrated exceptional antiproliferative action in HeLa cells while causing no harm in normal HaCat cell lines [24].

Gene therapy is a robust platform for molecularly inhibiting disease progression. Delivering siRNA/miRNA, on the other hand, has proven difficult, and several nanotechnology-based techniques have been utilised to successfully transport genes. Li *et al.*, placed heat shock protein-70 (Hsp-70) siRNA into polyethyleneimine modified SeNPs to kill HepG2 cells in order to test the survivability of SeNPs for gene delivery. Surprisingly, the NPs had a high transfection efficiency while also causing considerable cancer cell death through the induction of ROS and apoptosis [25].

SeNPs are possible drug carriers, and various studies have demonstrated their viability as a viable carrier. SeNPs treated with polyamidoamine dendrimers administered cisplatin and siRNA at the same time. In A549/DDP cells, it caused cell death via the PI3K/Akt/mTOR and MAPK/ERK pathways. Polyamidoamine modified SeNPs significantly transported siRNA and cisplatin to the tumour in a nude mouse model, with no systemic damage. Crocin delivery through PEG functionalized SeNPs was found to be effective for pH responsive delivery. The new NPs were found to destroy lung cancer cells effectively in vitro and in vivo in nude mice models via synergistic anticancer action. Mesoporous SeNPs have been described as a carrier for doxorubicin adminis-

tration to breast cancer patients with lower toxicity and improved anticancer activity [26]. Curcumin-loaded SeNPs were discovered to have promise anticancer efficacy in a mouse model of Ehrlich's ascites carcinoma, inducing apoptosis and reducing NF- κ B signaling as well as EMT [27]. Curcumin functionalized SeNPs were reported for enhanced chemopreventive activity [28].

SeNPs were found to protect against chromium-induced thyrotoxicity. In treated rats, SeNPs reduced K2Cr2O7-induced oxidative stress in the thyroid gland and restored T3, T4, superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase, and GSH levels. Additionally, SeNPs protected cellular integrity, avoided cell damage, and blocked thyroid alterations [29]. Melatonin-SeNPs were found to protect mice from immunological liver injury caused by BCG and LPS. BCG/LPS induces oxidative stress, and SeNPs and melatonin produce a new complex with synergistic antioxidant action that reduces it. Melatonin has been shown in previous research to protect the liver from harm through its direct antioxidant and immunoregulatory properties. Melatonin-SeNPs treatment increased the activity of antioxidant enzymes like SOD and GPX, decreased serum ALT, AST, NO, MDA levels, liver pathological abnormalities, proinflammatory cytokines [30].

Kumar *et al.*, investigated the preventive impact of SeNPs on diabetic nephropathy development. SeNPs reduced oxidative stress and increased the activity of cytoprotective protein Hsp-70, longevity protein Sirt1, and regulated the expression of apoptotic protein Bax and anti-apoptotic protein Bcl-2 in apoptotic kidney in streptozotocin-induced diabetic nephropathy. The effects, on the other hand, were unrelated to selenoprotein concentration or a conventional inorganic Se source [31]. Peptide conjugated chitosan modified with vasoactive intestinal peptide receptor 2 agonist SeNPs were discovered to have selective anti-diabetic action. Proliferation, glucose and insulin uptake, as well as intracellular oxidative stress, were all observed to be improved by the NPs. [32]. SeNPs have been postulated as a possible carrier for oral insulin delivery in a recent breakthrough. The NPs were found to exhibit synergistic anti-diabetic effect, enhanced pancreatic islet function, and boosted glucose utilisation [33].

Conclusion

There is limited awareness amongst dental students about use of Selenium nanoparticles therapy in medical applications. Enhanced awareness initiatives and dental educational programmes together with increased importance for curricular improvements that further promote knowledge and awareness of Selenium nanoparticles therapy.

References

- [1]. Liong M, Lu J, Kovichich M, Xia T, Ruehm SG, Nel AE, Tamaoui F, Zink JI. Multifunctional inorganic nanoparticles for imaging, targeting, and drug delivery. *ACS Nano*. 2008 May;2(5):889-96. Pubmed PMID: 19206485.
- [2]. Saifi MA, Sangomla S, Khurana A, Godugu C. Protective Effect of Nanoceria on Cisplatin-Induced Nephrotoxicity by Amelioration of Oxidative Stress and Pro-inflammatory Mechanisms. *Biol Trace Elem Res*. 2019 May;189(1):145-156. Pubmed PMID: 30047078.
- [3]. Moghimi SM, Hunter AC, Murray JC. Nanomedicine: current status and future prospects. *FASEB J*. 2005 Mar;19(3):311-30. Pubmed PMID: 15746175.
- [4]. Rayman MP. The importance of selenium to human health. *Lancet*. 2000 Jul 15;356(9225):233-41. Pubmed PMID: 10963212.
- [5]. Fernandes AP, Gandin V. Selenium compounds as therapeutic agents in cancer. *Biochim Biophys Acta*. 2015 Aug;1850(8):1642-60. Pubmed PMID: 25459512.
- [6]. Wang H, Zhang J, Yu H. Elemental selenium at nano size possesses lower toxicity without compromising the fundamental effect on selenoenzymes: comparison with selenomethionine in mice. *Free Radic Biol Med*. 2007 May 15;42(10):1524-33. Pubmed PMID: 17448899.
- [7]. Wang H, Wei W, Zhang SY, Shen YX, Yue L, Wang NP, Xu SY. Melatonin-selenium nanoparticles inhibit oxidative stress and protect against hepatic injury induced by Bacillus Calmette-Guérin/lipopolysaccharide in mice. *J Pineal Res*. 2005 Sep;39(2):156-63. Pubmed PMID: 16098093.
- [8]. Li Y, Li X, Wong YS, Chen T, Zhang H, Liu C, Zheng W. The reversal of cisplatin-induced nephrotoxicity by selenium nanoparticles functionalized with 11-mercaptop-1-undecanol by inhibition of ROS-mediated apoptosis. *Biomaterials*. 2011 Dec;32(34):9068-76. Pubmed PMID: 21864903.
- [9]. Hemalatha R, Ganapathy D. Disinfection of Dental Impression- A Current Overview. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 2016 Jul;8(7):661-4.
- [10]. Ramya G, Pandurangan K, Ganapathy D. Correlation between anterior crowding and bruxism-related parafunctional habits. *Drug Invention Today*. 2019 Oct 15;12(10).
- [11]. Anjum AS, Ganapathy D, Kumar K. Knowledge of the awareness of dentists on the management of burn injuries on the face. *Drug Invention Today*. 2019 Sep 1;11(9).
- [12]. Inchara R, Ganapathy D, Kumar PK. Preference of antibiotics in pediatric dentistry. *Drug Invent Today*. 2019 Jun 15;11:1495-8.
- [13]. Philip JM, Ganapathy DM, Ariga P. Comparative evaluation of tensile bond strength of a polyvinyl acetate-based resilient liner following various denture base surface pre-treatment methods and immersion in artificial salivary medium: An in vitro study. *Contemp Clin Dent*. 2012 Jul;3(3):298-301. Pubmed PMID: 23293485.
- [14]. Gupta A, Dhanraj M, Sivagami G. Implant surface modification: review of literature. *The Internet Journal of Dental Science*. 2009;7(1):10.
- [15]. Indhulekha V, Ganapathy D, Jain AR. Knowledge and awareness on biomedical waste management among students of four dental colleges in Chennai, India. *Drug Invention Today*. 2018 Dec 1;10(12):32-41.
- [16]. Mohamed Usman JA, Ayappan A, Ganapathy D, Nasir NN. Oromaxillary prosthetic rehabilitation of a maxillectomy patient using a magnet retained two-piece hollow bulb definitive obturator; a clinical report. *Case Rep Dent*. 2013;2013:190180. Pubmed PMID: 23533823.
- [17]. Ganapathy DM, Joseph S, Ariga P, Selvaraj A. Evaluation of the influence of blood glucose level on oral candidal colonization in complete denture wearers with Type-II Diabetes Mellitus: An in vivo Study. *Dent Res J (Isfahan)*. 2013 Jan;10(1):87-92. Pubmed PMID: 23878569.
- [18]. Menon A, Ganapathy DM, Mallikarjuna AV. Factors that influence the colour stability of composite resins. *Drug Innovation Today*. 2019 Mar 1;11(3).
- [19]. Dhanraj G, Rajeshkumar S. Anticariogenic Effect of Selenium Nanoparticles Synthesized Using Brassica oleracea. *Journal of Nanomaterials*. 2021 Jul 10;2021.
- [20]. Ganapathy D, Shanmugam R, Thangavelu L. Nanobiotechnology in combating CoVid-19. *Bioinformation*. 2020;16(11):828-30.
- [21]. Pi J, Yang F, Jin H, Huang X, Liu R, Yang P, Cai J. Selenium nanoparticles induced membrane bio-mechanical property changes in MCF-7 cells by disturbing membrane molecules and F-actin. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*. 2013 Dec 1;23(23):6296-303. Pubmed PMID: 24140445.
- [22]. Shakibaie M, Khorramizadeh MR, Faramarzi MA, Sabzevari O, Shahverdi AR. Biosynthesis and recovery of selenium nanoparticles and the effects on matrix metalloproteinase-2 expression. *Biotechnol Appl Biochem*. 2010 May 14;56(1):7-15. Pubmed PMID: 20408816.
- [23]. Ramya S, Shanmugasundaram T, Balagurunathan R. Biomedical potential of actinobacterially synthesized selenium nanoparticles with special reference to anti-biofilm, anti-oxidant, wound healing, cytotoxic and anti-viral activities. *J Trace Elem Med Biol*. 2015 Oct;32:30-9. Pubmed PMID: 26302909.
- [24]. Srivastava P, Braganca JM, Kowshik M. In vivo synthesis of selenium nanoparticles by *Halococcus salifodinae* BK18 and their anti-proliferative properties against HeLa cell line. *Biotechnol Prog*. 2014 Nov;30(6):1480-7.
- [25]. Li Y, Lin Z, Zhao M, Xu T, Wang C, Xia H, Wang H, Zhu B. Multifunctional selenium nanoparticles as carriers of HSP70 siRNA to induce apoptosis of HepG2 cells. *Int J Nanomedicine*. 2016 Jul 5;11:3065-76. Pubmed PMID: 27462151.
- [26]. Zhao S, Yu Q, Pan J, Zhou Y, Cao C, Ouyang JM, Liu J. Redox-responsive mesoporous selenium delivery of doxorubicin targets MCF-7 cells and synergistically enhances its anti-tumor activity. *Acta Biomater*. 2017 May;54:294-306. Pubmed PMID: 28267598.
- [27]. Rustum YM. Pleiotropic Action of Selenium in the Prevention and Treatment of Cancer, and Related Diseases. MDPI-Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute; 2019 Mar 26.
- [28]. Pathak YV, editor. Surface modification of nanoparticles for targeted drug delivery. Springer; 2019 Mar 11.
- [29]. Hassanin KM, Abd El-Kawi SH, Hashem KS. The prospective protective effect of selenium nanoparticles against chromium-induced oxidative and cellular damage in rat thyroid. *Int J Nanomedicine*. 2013;8:1713-20. Pubmed PMID: 23658489.
- [30]. Wang H, Wei W, Zhang SY, Shen YX, Wang NP, Yue L, Xu SY. Melatonin-selenium nanoparticles protects liver against immunological injury induced by bacillus Calmette-Guerin and lipopolysaccharide. *Acta Pharmacol Sin*. 2005 Jun;26(6):745-52. Pubmed PMID: 15916742.
- [31]. Kumar GS, Kulkarni A, Khurana A, Kaur J, Tikoo K. Selenium nanoparticles involve HSP-70 and SIRT1 in preventing the progression of type 1 diabetic nephropathy. *Chem Biol Interact*. 2014 Nov 5;223:125-33. Pubmed PMID: 25301743.
- [32]. Zhao SJ, Wang DH, Li YW, Han L, Xiao X, et al. A novel selective VPAC2 agonist peptide-conjugated chitosan modified selenium nanoparticles with enhanced anti-type 2 diabetes synergy effects. *Int J Nanomedicine*. 2017 Mar 20;12:2143-2160. Pubmed PMID: 28356733.
- [33]. Deng W, Xie Q, Wang H, Ma Z, Wu B, Zhang X. Selenium nanoparticles as versatile carriers for oral delivery of insulin: Insight into the synergic anti-diabetic effect and mechanism. *Nanomedicine*. 2017 Aug;13(6):1965-1974. PMID: 28539272.